

Understanding the climate change in North Central Province of Sri Lanka by analyzing the trends of rainfall, temperature and relative humidity

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The trend analysis of meteorological data is important to understand climate change. In this study, the rainfall, temperature and relative humidity parameters were used to understand the climate change in the North Central Province of Sri Lanka. The study was conducted district wise by using historical data from 1993 to 2023. The combination of satellite data and meteorological station data were used for the trend analysis. Statistical trend analysis techniques, namely linear regression, Mann-Kendall's test and Sen's slope estimator were used in the study. The linear regression method was used to identify the relationship between rainfall, temperature and relative humidity over time. The non-parametric tests including the Mann-Kendall test and Sen's slope estimator were used to identify the direction and magnitude of the trend respectively. The results revealed significant increasing trends in maximum temperature and rainfall and a significant decreasing trend in minimum temperature for both districts at 95% confidence limit. Relative humidity trends varied, with Anuradhapura showing a significant increase and Polonnaruwa showing a nonsignificant increase. The ARIMA model was used to predict the future trends of the parameters until 2033. According to the ARIMA findings, the annual average values for rainfall, maximum temperature, minimum temperature and relative humidity for Anuradhapura and Polonnaruwa districts would be 3344 mm, 34.6 °C, 26.3 °C, 84.5% and 3358 mm, 34.8 °C, 26.9 °C and 83% respectively by the year 2033. The findings of this study are valuable for researchers and policymakers to understand climate change in the region.

Keywords: Trend analysis; Mann-Kendall's test; Sen's slope estimator; arima

Underlined is the presenting author.